

FURTHER EVALUATION OF PROPOSED BIAXIAL STRESS TEST SPECIMEN FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Finite element analyses were made of a new test specimen proposed for the evaluation of composite material properties under biaxial stress conditions. Examination of the stress distributions in the gage section for both isotropic and composite materials revealed rather significant variations in the principal stress components as well as the principal stress ratio and that the state of stress is dependent on the material properties. It was also observed that the assumption of uniform stresses based on force equilibrium is invalid, except for the pure shear case corresponding to 0 deg. loading. Based on these analyses and some test results, it was concluded that this specimen is unsuitable for strength measurements, but may have limited application for evaluation of elastic constants under biaxial stress conditions, particularly the determination of the in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} .

INTRODUCTION

In the evaluation of composite material properties under uniaxial stress conditions, the specimen design and test techniques are relatively straightforward. For biaxial loading, however, the test apparatus can become quite complex depending on the desired stress condition. Commonly, combined loading of tubes or cylinders and biaxial loading of plates are often used for such evaluations.

Arcan, Hashin and Voloshin⁽¹⁾ in a recent paper proposed a new test specimen for the determination of composite material properties under biaxial plane stress conditions. The test specimen, shown in Fig. 1, consists of a disc having anti-symmetric cutouts which is diametrically loaded. Depending on the loading angle α , specific biaxial stress conditions, including pure shear, are produced in the gage section, AB, by virtue of the geometry. In principal, this specimen has a number of advantages; (1) simple loading requirements, (2) relatively low specimen preparation cost with the availability of numerical controlled machining techniques, (3) a fairly wide range of biaxial stress ratios are possible, (4) a pure shear stress state can be generated.

Fig. 1 - Plane stress test specimen (Arcan, et. al. , Ref 1)

This last advantage may be quite significant in that most of the common test methods for determination of in-plane shear properties, such as ± 45 deg. tensile specimens, off-axis loaded tensile specimens and even the rail shear method are all compromises to some extent to a pure shear stress condition.

The intent of this paper is to further evaluate this test specimen using finite-element analyses for isotropic and typical composite materials in combination with some experimental results.

TEST SPECIMEN

The dimensions shown in Fig. 1 are based on certain optimum geometric ratios given in Ref. 1, using an arbitrarily selected diameter, D , of 139.7 mm. The gage section AB is bounded by $x = \pm d_2/2$, and $y = \pm d_1/2$.

From a photoelastic analysis it was shown that as the loading angle, α , is varied, the maximum shear stress, $(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)/2$ remains uniform along section AB and that the principal stress directions are always at ± 45 deg. These conditions, of course, cannot be satisfied within some transition region in the vicinity of the free boundaries of the section.

From equilibrium considerations and assumed uniform stresses along AB (the authors did not separate and examine the individual stress components from the photoelastic analysis):

$$\sigma_x^u = \frac{P}{td_1} \sin \alpha \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^u = \frac{P}{td_1} \cos \alpha \quad (2)$$

where t is the specimen thickness. If the principal stresses are oriented at ± 45 deg., then $\sigma_x = \sigma_y$ and the principal stresses are given by

$$\sigma_{1,2}^u = \sigma_x \pm \tau_{xy} \quad (3)$$

Using Eqs. (1) and (2), the ratio of principal stresses can be written as

$$K = \sigma_1/\sigma_2 = \frac{\tan \alpha + 1}{\tan \alpha - 1} \quad (4)$$

In a later paper⁽²⁾, Voloshin and Arcan suggest that for loading angles $|\alpha| > 25$ deg., the specimen is unsuitable because of non-uniform stress conditions in the gage section. For this range of α , the stress ratio varies as

$$-2.7 < K < -0.36 \quad (5)$$

For completeness, loading angles outside of this range will be included in this paper.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A finite element model of the test specimen in Fig. 1 was constructed and the element mesh is shown in Fig. 2. It was necessary to model only one-half of the specimen because of its anti-symmetric characteristics. The model contained 848 quadrilateral constant strain elements and 927 nodal points. The adequacy of this model was demonstrated by performing a comparative analysis where the identical mesh was used except that isoparametric quadrilateral elements were selected. Isotropic material properties were used in these analyses and there was negligible difference in the results. The mesh contained 11 elements through one-half of the gage section AB. The element closest to the radius r , was one-half the dimension in the y direction of the element closest to $y = 0$.

Fig. 2 - Finite element model of test specimen

The WECAN (Westinghouse Electric Computer Analysis) general purpose finite element program⁽³⁾ was used in the analysis. The specimen was considered to be in a condition of plane stress. Boundary conditions were applied which would enforce the anti-symmetric condition existing along the $y = 0$ boundary of the model. At the node, $x = y = 0$, the displacements u_x and u_y were constrained. The mesh was constructed so that there were an identical number of equidistant nodal points along the $y = 0$ line on either side of the y -axis. Linear constraint equations were applied to each set of nodes so that $u_x(x) = -u_x(-x)$ and $u_y(x) = -u_y(-x)$. The load, P , was applied at selected nodes near the outer diameter of the specimen. In order to remove rigid body motion from the model, one additional degree-of-freedom needed to be constrained anywhere in the model. The nodal point at which the load was applied was constrained so that it could only move radially outward on a line passing through $x = y = 0$.

Various analyses were made using both isotropic and orthotropic material properties and are described in the following sections.

Isotropic Material

The distributions of shear stress, principal stress direction and principal stress ratio in the gage section of the specimen for the 0 deg. loading angle are shown in Fig. 3 as the solid curves. Stresses are normalized in terms of the uniform shear stress given by Eq. (2). The abscissa is based on half of the gage section length, $d_1/2$. Since constant strain elements were used in the analysis, nodal point stresses along the centerline of the gage section are obtained by averaging surrounding element stresses.

It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the shear stress, τ_{xy} , varies less than 5 percent to within about one-radius of the boundary at $2y/d_1 = 0.80$. The principal stress direction, θ , and principal stress ratio, K , indicate a relatively pure state of shear in over 90 percent of the section. For convenience in discussing variations in the section, we will arbitrarily define an "effective" gage length equal to 80 percent of the total length, d_1 .

Fig. 3 — Distribution of shear stress, principal stress direction and principal stress ratio in gage section of specimen for loading angle of 0° . Comparison of isotropic and orthotropic solutions

The solid curves in Fig. 4 show results of the analysis for a loading angle of 30° deg. The principal stress components are given in terms of the assumed uniform stress, σ^u , as computed from Eq. (3). At center of the section, σ_2 exceeds the nominal value by 50 percent, while σ_1 is 14 percent higher. Within the effective gage length, σ_1 , σ_2 , K and θ do not vary by more than 15 percent. At the free boundary, $2y/d_1 = 1$, K becomes infinite as a result of the vanishing stress component, $\sigma_y = \sigma_2$.

Fig. 4 — Distribution of principal stresses, principal stress ratio and principal stress direction in gage section of specimen for loading angle of 30° . Comparison of isotropic and orthotropic solutions.

The upper portion of Table 1 summarizes the results of the isotropic analyses for loading angles $-30 < \alpha < 40$ deg. An indication of the variation within the effective gage length is seen by comparing the results at $2y/d_1 = 0$ and 0.8.

It can be seen that the principal stresses differ considerably from the uniform stress assumption, particularly at the larger loading angles. The deviation is largest in σ_2 for positive loading angles and in σ_1 for negative loading angles. Also, the variation within the gage action increases as the loading angle increases. The principal stress differences, $(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)$, however, are quite uniform through the section, which is in agreement with the photoelastic observations reported in Ref. 1. Note that the principal stress directions are at ± 45 deg. for all loading angles at the center of the section. The principal stress ratio, K , at the center of the specimen as determined from these analyses is shown as one of the solid curves in Fig. 5, where a comparison is made with the value of K based on uniform stress assumptions, Eq. (4). There is an obvious difference, as much as nearly 75 percent at $\alpha = 30$ deg. For $-15 < \alpha < 15$ deg., the maximum error in K by assuming uniform conditions would be 30 percent.

Fig. 5 - Variation of principal stress ratio at center of gage section with loading angle. Comparison of uniform stress assumption with results of finite element analysis and measured values.

Unidirectional Composites

Finite element analyses were also made for glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy materials. The orthotropic material properties used are shown in Table 2. The properties for the glass/epoxy were obtained from basic lamina tests while those for graphite/epoxy were taken from the literature as being typical. Only unidirectional laminates were considered with the fiber angle, β , defined as in Fig. 1.

Considering first the case of $\beta = 90$ deg. (fibers in y-direction), the results for $\alpha = 0$ deg. are shown as points in Fig. 3 where they are compared to the isotropic material case. In general, there are only small differences between the two orthotropic materials. Comparison with the isotropic material shows that the orthotropy does influence the state of stress in the specimen, although for this loading angle, the assumption of pure shear is still reasonable. The difference is more evident at larger loading angles, as shown in Fig. 4 for $\alpha = 30$ deg. For this case,

	Loading angle, α , deg. \rightarrow	0		15		30		40		-15		-30	
	$2y/d_1 \rightarrow$	0	0.8	0	0.8	0	0.8	0	0.8	0	0.8	0	0.8
Isotropic	σ_1/σ_1^u	1.05	1.01	0.95	0.98	0.86	0.97	0.82	0.96	1.24	1.07	1.76	1.27
	σ_2/σ_2^u	0.95	1.04	1.10	1.11	1.50	1.34	2.10	2.28	0.87	1.00	0.81	0.99
	$(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)/(\sigma_1^u - \sigma_2^u)$	1.00	1.03	1.00	1.03	1.10	1.05	1.01	1.07	1.00	1.03	1.01	1.05
	$K = \sigma_1/\sigma_2$	-1.11	-0.97	-1.49	-1.53	-2.16	-2.70	-3.04	-4.85	-0.83	-0.62	-0.58	-0.35
	θ , deg.	44	44	44	42	43	39	42	37	43	42	42	39
Glass/epoxy $\beta = 90^\circ$	σ_1/σ_1^u	1.04	0.91	0.96	0.91	0.91	0.91	---	---	1.18	0.92	1.55	0.97
	σ_2/σ_2^u	1.10	0.96	1.26	0.99	1.69	1.10	---	---	1.01	0.94	0.94	0.94
	$K = \sigma_1/\sigma_2$	-0.94	-0.94	-1.33	-1.58	-2.01	-3.08	---	---	-0.67	-0.56	-0.44	-0.28
	θ , deg.	44	44	44	42	43	39	---	---	44	42	45	40

σ_1^u and σ_2^u given by Eq. (3)

Table 1 - Results of Finite-Element Analysis of Test Specimen for Isotropic and Glass/Epoxy Materials

		<u>Glass/Epoxy</u>	<u>Graphite/Epoxy</u>
Elastic Constants	E_1 , GPa	40.7	137.9
	E_2 , GPa	9.0	9.7
	ν_{12}	0.27	0.31
	G_{12} , GPa	4.1	4.2
Strengths	S_1 , MPa	1365	1448
	S_1' , MPa	620	1448
	S_2 , MPa	28	48
	S_2' , MPa	103	145
	S_{12} , MPa	69	90
Strength Coefficients	F_{11} , MPa^{-2}	1.2×10^{-6}	4.8×10^{-7}
	F_{22} , MPa^{-2}	3.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}
	F_1 , MPa^{-1}	-8.8×10^{-4}	0
	F_2 , MPa^{-1}	2.6×10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-2}
	F_{66} , MPa^{-2}	2.2×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-4}
	F_{12} , MPa^{-2}	0	0

- (1) primes denote compression properties
- (2) F_i and F_{ij} used in failure analysis
- (3) subscripts 1 and 2 denote fiber and transverse directions, respectively
- (4) subscript 12 denotes in-plane shear

Table 2 - Mechanical Properties of SP-250-S2 Glass/Epoxy and 3501-6/AS Graphite/Epoxy Unidirectional Laminates

the deviation from the uniform stress assumption for σ_2 is nearly 70 percent at the center of the specimen. Also, the variation within the effective gage length is more severe. Conversely, σ_1 becomes more uniform in the orthotropic material. The principal stress angle, θ_1 however, remains close to 45 deg.

The lower portion of Table 1 shows results of the analyses of the glass/epoxy composite for loading angles of 0, ± 15 and ± 30 deg. Comparison with the isotropic case shows a significant difference in the state of stress in the section as a result of the orthotropic behavior. In general, variations in the stress components across the gage section were somewhat more severe for the composite material, again at the larger loading angles. The variation in the principal stress ratio, K, at the center of the section for the glass/epoxy composite is shown by the dashed curve in Fig. 5. Comparing the two materials, K for the composite is 7 percent lower at $\alpha = 30$ deg. and 24 percent lower at $\alpha = -30$ deg.

The case of $\beta = 0$ deg. (fibers in x-direction) was analyzed only for the glass/epoxy composite at $\alpha = 0$ deg. and these results are included in Fig. 3. At the center, K is -1.14 indicating a larger deviation from the pure shear case than for $\beta = 90$ deg. While no analyses were made for other loading angles, it would seem that the trends observed for $\beta = 90$ deg. would hold for this case also.

In Ref. 1, the authors suggested that the gage section is contained within a region called the "significant sample" having a width d_2 (see Fig. 1). Figure 6 shows the variation of the shear stress in the x direction at two locations for the glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy materials with the load applied at $\alpha = 0$ deg. Within d_2 , the shear stress ratio varies from 0.71 to 1.04 for the graphite/epoxy and from 0.84 to 1.07 for the glass epoxy, considering the worst condition.

Fig. 6 - Shear stress distribution across gage section of composite specimen showing variation within the "significant sample", d_2 , defined in Ref. 1

From the above analyses, it was observed that the principal stress direction does indeed remain relatively constant at 45 deg. within the gage action of the specimen. Thus, a possible application for this specimen is in the evaluation of biaxial states of stress relative to the lamina principal axes. This can be achieved by orienting the fibers in the principal stress directions at $\beta = 45$ deg. or -45 deg. Since σ_1 is always positive, the widest range of stress ratios can be obtained by using $\beta = -45$ deg. for $\alpha > 0$ and 45 deg. for $\alpha < 0$. These two conditions produce stress states in the fourth and second quadrants, respectively of the lamina biaxial stress plane.

Finite element analyses were made for these two fiber angles for both composite materials. Figure 7 shows some typical stress distributions in the gage section; in this case for graphite/epoxy with $\alpha = 15$ deg. and $\beta = -45$ deg. Here, σ_1 and σ_2 refer to the principal axes of the laminate; however, these are close to the principal stresses. For these cases, the stresses vary significantly over quite a large portion of the gage length and again, the condition worsens as the loading angle increases. Similar behavior was observed for glass/epoxy.

The variation of stress ratio K (relative to the lamina axes) at the center of the gage section is shown in Fig. 8 for both materials. Again, the uniform stress assumption can be seen to be invalid.

Fig. 7 — Distribution of stresses, stress ratio and principal stress direction in gage section of graphite/epoxy composite specimen. Stresses are in the principal directions of the lamina. Loading angle $\alpha = 15^\circ$, Fiber direction $\beta = -45^\circ$.

Fig. 8 — Variation of principal stress ratio at center of gage section with loading angle for graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy specimen with fiber angle of 45° . Comparison of finite element, measured values and uniform stress assumption.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

Using the Tsai-Wu tensor-polynomial failure theory⁽⁴⁾, a failure analysis of the gage section and the adjacent fillet region of the specimen was made using the results of the finite element analysis. In terms of the principal material directions of the lamina, this failure criterion for plane stress conditions can be written as

$$f(\sigma_{ij}) = F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_1\sigma_1 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 \quad (6)$$

where the coefficients, F_{11} and F_{ij} , can be shown to be functions of the simple engineering strengths of the lamina⁽⁴⁾; for example:

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{S_1^2}, \text{ and } F_1 = \frac{1}{S_1} - \frac{1}{S_1}$$

The values of these coefficients are given in Table 2 for the two materials.

Failure is assumed when $f(\sigma_{ij}) \geq 1$. Defining a safety margin, $S = \sigma_f/\sigma_a$ where σ_f is the failure stress and σ_a is the applied stress, and assuming proportional loading such that

$$\frac{\sigma_{1f}}{\sigma_{1a}} = \frac{\sigma_{2f}}{\sigma_{2a}} = \frac{\tau_{12f}}{\tau_{12a}} = S \quad (7)$$

failure occurs when $\sigma_{ia} = \sigma_{if}$ or $S = 1$. Substituting the applied stresses from Eq. (7), the failure criterion can be expressed in terms of the safety margin, thus:

$$(F_{11}\sigma_{1a}^2 + F_{22}\sigma_{2a}^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_{1a}\sigma_{2a} + F_{66}\tau_{12a}^2)S^2 + (F_1\sigma_{1a} + F_2\sigma_{2a})S = 1 \quad (8)$$

The two roots of this quadratic equation give the safety margins for the applied stress state and an equal stress state of opposite sign. Tsai and Hahn⁽⁵⁾ have suggested this approach for strength analysis of composite structures.

Equation (8) was incorporated into a finite element post-processor program for evaluation of the stress conditions at each element. For a given loading, comparison of the relative magnitudes of S at various locations can show the probable failure points.

Figure 9 shows the variation of the ratio S/S_0 along the gage section and on the boundary of the cutout for glass/epoxy with $\beta = 90$ deg. and graphite/epoxy with $\beta = -45$ deg., where S_0 is the safety margin at the center of the gage section. Three loading angles are shown. In the gage section it can be seen that for $\beta = 90$ deg., as the loading angle increases, the probable failure location shifts to the boundary where the state of stress is highly non-uniform.

The important observation to be made here concerns the local minimum in the ratio occurring on the boundary in the vicinity of the tangent point of the fillet radius. Although the location and relative magnitude of this minimum point varied somewhat with loading angle, material and fiber orientation, it was present in all the cases analyzed. It was concluded that failure could very well occur at this point where the state of stress is considerably different than in the gage section. Indeed, this location was verified experimentally, as will be described in the following section.

EXPERIMENTAL

A limited number of tests were performed on unidirectional glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy specimens. Specimens (as in Fig. 1) were machined from 8 or 10 ply laminates prepared from pre-preg tape using conventional fabrication processes. Machining was done on a tape-controlled milling machine with a carbide cutter and special alignment jigs. Minimal machining time was required with this procedure.

Fig. 9 - Variation of safety factor in gage section, bottom, and on boundary of cutout, top, for glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy specimens based on Tsai-Wu failure theory. Fiber angle $\beta = 90^\circ$ or -45°

From the analyses, it was observed that under all loading angles, a rather severe stress concentration occurred on the boundary of the cutouts as a result of bending; thus $+90$ deg. glass/epoxy reinforcing plates were cemented to a portion of the specimen. These can be seen in Fig. 10.

Tests were made with fiber angles of 0, 90, 45 and -45 deg. and various loading angles. Three-element 0.81 mm strain gage rosettes, oriented at 0 and $+45$ deg. relative to the x axis, were employed at the center of the gage section for strain measurement. Measured strains were transformed to the principal lamina directions and the orthotropic stress-strain relations⁽⁹⁾:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

were then used to determine stresses. The Q_{ij} terms of the stiffness matrix are functions of the elastic constants⁽⁶⁾.

The behavior of the glass/epoxy specimen for various loading angles was examined for a 90 deg. fiber angle. The values of the principal stress ratio as computed from strain measurements are shown as the open points in Fig. 5. Because of the relative magnitudes and signs of the three measured strains, small errors in each component may produce quite large errors in the principal strains calculated through the standard rosette analysis equations. In view of this, the agreement with the finite-element analysis is considered good.

Table 3 summarizes additional test results for specimens with either a 0 or 90 deg. fiber angle. The in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , was determined from strain measurements for a loading angle of 0 deg.:

$$G_{12} = \frac{\tau_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} = \frac{P_o}{d_1 t (\epsilon_{+45} - \epsilon_{-45})} \quad (10)$$

where P_o is the load, d_1 is the gage section length, t is the specimen thickness and α_{+45} and α_{-45} are the strains at ± 45 deg. which were very close to the principal values. No correction was made for the slight deviation from pure shear conditions at the center of the specimen predicted by the analysis (see Fig. 3). For the glass/epoxy composite, the range of values represents 5 tests, 2 of which included a 0 deg. fiber angle, while the value of G_{12} for graphite/epoxy is based on only a single test. These properties are slightly higher than those used in the analysis, Table 2, but are certainly within an acceptable range for these materials.

Fig. 10 - Glass/epoxy test specimens with fiber angle $\beta = 90^\circ$
Failure under (a) 0° loading and (b) 15° loading

Failure data for 0 and 15 deg. loading angles are shown in Table 3. Reported are the average shear stress based on Eq. (2), and the locations of the failures, which as can be seen from Fig. 10, were generally not at the center of the section. The probable failure point on the cutout boundary predicted in the failure analysis was, on the average, about 1.02 mm, which is within the range of the measured locations. This suggests that the failure mode is not the result of the stress state in the gage section but rather is the result of a more general state of stress existing at the

boundary. Additional support for this comes from inspection of the calculated shear strengths for $\alpha = 0$ deg. These are considerably lower than values of the in-plane shear strengths given in Table 2 which are typical for these materials.

	<u>Glass/epoxy</u>	<u>Graphite/epoxy</u>
G_{12} , GPa $\alpha = 0$ deg	4.8 - 5.1	5.2
Average shear stress at failure, τ_{12}^u , MPa $\alpha = 0^\circ$ $\alpha = 15^\circ$	42.0 - 51.7 31.7	50.3
Failure location *, mm $\alpha = 0^\circ$ $\alpha = 15^\circ$	1.02 - 1.62 1.04	1.45

*Distance from y-axis

Table 3 - Test Results for Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy and Graphite Epoxy Composite Specimens

The failure mode can be evaluated by inspection of the state of stress at the failure point. For glass/epoxy at $\alpha = 0$ deg., for example, at $\tau_{xy}^u = 49.6$ MPa, ratioing the finite element results assuming linear behavior gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y &= \sigma_1 = 44.2 \text{ MPa} \\ \sigma_x &= \sigma_2 = 42.0 \text{ MPa} \\ \tau_{xy} &= \tau_{12} = 35.9 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Evaluating the Tsai-Wu failure theory, Eq. (6), we obtain:

$$f(\sigma_{ij}) = [2.30 \times 10^{-3} - 3.90 \times 10^{-2}] + [0.61 + 1.092] + [0.28] = 1.94$$

which indicates failure has occurred. The terms in this equation have been bracketed to show the relative contributions of each stress component. The important observation here is that the transverse stress in the center set of brackets is the major contributor to failure. Thus we might conclude that the failures observed in the specimen are primarily transverse tension rather than shear.

Several tests were also made with fiber angles of 45 and -45 degrees for the graphite/epoxy material. The principal stress ratios computed from strain measurements are shown as the open points in Fig. 8. Agreement with the analysis is good. Attempts were made to fail these specimens at 15 and -15 deg. loading angles, but no observations regarding the mode of failure in or around the gage section could be made due to premature failures in the reinforcement areas.

CONCLUSIONS

Finite element analyses of the test specimen were made for isotropic and unidirectional composite materials assuming orthotropic behavior for the latter. In general, the results for glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy composites were confirmed experimentally. Based on this evaluation, the following comments are offered regarding the specimen:

- (1) The uniform stress assumption in the gage section, (Eqs. (1) - (3), is unrealistic for anything other than a loading angle of zero. While the maximum shear stress is quite uniform for the isotropic case, supporting the photoelastic analysis in Ref. 1, the individual stress components vary significantly. This variation becomes more severe as the loading angle increases.
- (2) For a unidirectional composite material, the state of stress is a function of both the lamina material properties and the fiber orientation. The principal stress ratio cannot be predicted by Eq. (4) which is based on a uniform stress assumption.
- (3) For the case of a 0 deg. loading angle, a nearly pure state of shear is produced in over 80 percent of the gage section. Thus, measurements of the in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , should be quite good with this specimen.
- (4) Failure for small loading angles originates on the boundary near the fillet at the end of the gage section. A failure analysis confirmed this location. For a 90 deg. fiber angle, and small loading angles, the failure mode is primarily transverse tension rather than shear. Thus the specimen is unsuitable for determination of in-plane shear strength. With a fiber angle of 0 deg., failures occurred away from the gage section.
- (5) The specimen may be useful in some cases for evaluation of elastic properties under biaxial loading conditions, but consideration must be given to the lack of a uniform stress state in the gage section and the fact that this state cannot be determined from simple load-geometry relationships.

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